

VALORISATION OF FOOD LOSS INTO SUSTAINABLE ACTIVE PACKAGING: POLYLACTIC ACID COATING WITH ARTICHOKE LEAF EXTRACT AND CARBOXYMETHYL CELLULOSE

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Abstract: Food loss and waste is a major global problem, yet it contains valuable compounds with antioxidant and antimicrobial properties that can be sustainably valorized. Incorporating such compounds into an active packaging system offers a dual benefit: reducing waste while extending food shelf life. In this study we developed and characterized polylactic acid (PLA) coated packaging using artichoke leaves extract (ALE) and carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) for enhanced antioxidant and antibacterial properties. ALE was obtained through subcritical water extraction, and PLA clamshell surfaces were first modified with spray-coating PLA-polyethylene glycol (PEG) solution to improve coating adherence. Coating solutions of CMC and ALE at different ratios (70:30, 60:40, and 50:50 w/w) were then applied in multiple layers. Surface modification with PLA-PEG increased wettability and facilitate uniform coating formation. Incorporation of ALE altered packaging color, increasing red and yellow hues proportionally to its concentration. SEM imaging confirmed a smooth, pore-free coating on modified surfaces, while unmodified or CMC-only were uneven. Functional testing showed that PLA-PEG modification reduced water vapor permeability by 36%, although the hydrophilic CMC-ALE coatings increased moisture uptake. Antioxidant activity, measured by DPPH assay, reached 40–44% scavenging after 15 min, and increased to 54–67% after 45 min, indicating sustained release of phenolic and flavonoid compounds. Antibacterial assays revealed concentration-dependent inhibition of *E. coli* (0.9–2.1 log reduction) and moderate reduction of *S. aureus* (~1 log), likely due to polyphenol-mediated disruption of bacterial membranes. Overall, the results demonstrate the potential of ALE-based coatings in PLA packaging to extend shelf-life and preserve food quality through combined antioxidant and antibacterial effects.

Keywords: active packaging, coating, artichoke leaf, polylactic acid, antioxidant activity, antibacterial activity

1 INTRODUCTION

Food loss and waste across the food supply chain pose serious global challenges, contributing significantly to environmental degradation and greenhouse gas emissions (Read et al., 2020). According to the FAO, nearly one-third of all food produced worldwide is lost or wasted each year (FAO, 2011), with approximately 58 million tonnes generated annually in the European Union (Eurostat, 2022). Among these, fruits and vegetables account for the highest proportion of losses around 41% and 46%, respectively at various stages including primary production, processing, distribution, and consumption (Caldeira et al., 2019). To address this issue, it is essential to shift from

the traditional linear economy model of “take, make, and dispose” towards a circular economy approach. For instance, plant residues such as artichoke leaves are largely discarded during harvesting and preparation. The global artichoke production reaching 1,978 kton annually, of which 70–80% is wasted as leaves, stems, and roots (Bittencourt et al., 2023). Notably, artichoke leaves are rich in bioactive compounds such as polysaccharides and phenolics with promising functional potential.

Meanwhile, the food packaging industry is increasingly seeking sustainable active packaging materials that can extend shelf life, maintain food quality, and reduce food waste at the retail and consumption stages (Momtaz et al., 2024). Valorizing food losses generated during raw material production, processing, and distribution for such applications further enhances the environmental and economic impact of active packaging innovations (Bhargava et al., 2020; Riaz et al., 2024).

Active packaging can be developed by adding active agents to the material or applying them as surface coatings. These agents provide specific functions, such as absorbing or scavenging substances like moisture, flavors, gases, or UV light, releasing compounds such as antioxidants and antibacterials (John et al., 2023). Surface coating is preferable for heat-sensitive natural compounds, as it preserves their functionality, maintains the material’s properties, and allows better food contact and controlled release of actives (Bastarrachea et al., 2015; John et al., 2023). Several techniques including spraying, electrospraying, dipping, cast coating, chemical vapor deposition, physical vapor deposition, roll-to-roll, and screen printing have been used for coating applications (Vasile, 2018). For example, natural plant polyphenol proanthocyanidins and layered clays were incorporated into poly (vinyl alcohol)-based coatings applied to corona-treated polylactic acid (PLA) films using an automatic wire-bar coater, which significantly improved both active functions and gas barrier properties (Wang et al., 2023). In another study, cellulose nanocrystals modified with methacrylamide, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, or zinc oxide were spray-coated onto PLA films, resulting in excellent antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, improved mechanical properties, reduced gas permeability, faster compostability, and extended pork shelf life (Huang et al., 2023).

Therefore, the present study aims to develop a bioactive coating based on artichoke leaf extract (ALE), a valorized food loss stream, combined with carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), applied to PLA-based food containers. The functional and physical properties of the coated packaging were then evaluated.

Figure 1: Circular valorization of artichoke leaves extract in active food packaging

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Preparation of active packaging

ALE was obtained using subcritical water extraction technique at 150 °C and biomass to water ratio of 1:10 (g:mL) at two cycles of 20 min (1500 psi). The freeze-dried fraction obtained from second cycle was utilized in this research. In order to enhance the surface activity of the PLA-based clamshells before applying the active coating, it was modified by spraying the solution of 1 % (w/v) of PLA containing 20 % (w/w) of polyethylene glycol (PEG) on the surface of PLA clamshells using an airbrush connected to a vacuum air pump. Then, the coating solutions were prepared by mixing different ratios of CMC and ALE (e.i. 100:00, 70:30, 60:40, 50:50 w/w) and 30% (w/w) glycerol. The coating solution was sprayed at several layers on the modified PLA surface at distance of 15 cm and pressure of 2.5 bar (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Development of active layers composing of ALE and CMC on PLA based packaging using spray coating

2.2 Characterization of active packaging

The contact angle measurement was carried out using a tensiometer to investigate how surface modification affected the surface hydrophilicity of PLA-based clamshells. The surface microstructure and the morphology of the cross-section of the PLA-based clamshells before and after coating was observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Active packaging were then characterized for their color, hygroscopicity, water vapor permeability (WVP), antioxidant activity, and antibacterial activities.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Surface modification of PLA packaging by spraying PLA-PEG prior to applying active layer enhanced the wettability of the container surface to interact with the active coating layer. PLA-PEG modifying solution was compatible with the beneath PLA surface and including the PEG as shown in Figure 3 enhanced the surface hydrophilicity compared to the control samples by decreasing the contact angle.

Figure 3: Water contact angle of PLA based packaging (a) before and (b) after surface modification

The inclusion of ALE in the coating solutions changed the color parameters of packaging surface as shown in Table 1. ALE significantly reduced the brightness of packaging. The a^* factor showed all the films surface color were in greenish hue while the b^* factor showed yellowish hue in all samples. Increasing the ALE content in the coating enhanced both reddish and yellowish color which might be due to the contribution of phenolic compounds in ALE to the coloration of coatings. The overall color change (ΔE) of samples compared to the uncoated PLA showed enhancing the differences by increasing the ALE concentration as it was also observed in visual appearance of the corresponding coated packaging.

Table 1: Color parameters and colour differences of uncoated and coated PLA packagings

Samples	L^*	a^*	b^*	ΔE
PLA-C	84.98 ± 0.04^a	-1.83 ± 0.01^c	3.26 ± 0.03^f	reference
C:E (70:30)	77.84 ± 0.50^c	-0.86 ± 0.05^b	14.41 ± 0.12^c	13.28 ± 0.30^b
C:E (60:40)	76.16 ± 0.30^d	-0.63 ± 0.05^a	16.29 ± 0.33^b	15.79 ± 0.28^a
C:E (50:50)	76.31 ± 0.77^d	-0.66 ± 0.12^a	16.70 ± 0.31^a	16.05 ± 0.56^a

As shown in SEM images of uncoated and coated packaging (Figure 4), plain PLA presented a rough surface. CMC solution alone was not able to cover the whole surface (Figure 4e) due to higher viscosity and lower flowability. Substitution of ALE with CMC made a uniform and smooth coating covering the whole surface without any pores or cracks (Figure 4f). As shown in the cross-sectional SEM image, modification with PLA-PEG partially dissolved the underlying surface, and the thickness of the active layer was approximately 5 μm (Figure 4g).

Figure 4. Photographs (top) and SEM images of surface morphology (down, magnification $\times 1000$) of PLA-based packaging: (a,d) uncoated PLA, (b, e) coated with C:E (100:00), (c, f) coated with C:E (60:40), and (g) cross-sectional SEM image of coated PLA with C:E (70:30) representing different layers.

Regarding the WVP barrier, the uncoated PLA packaging showed the highest WVP values, while the surface modified PLA decreased the WVP significantly by 36%. Introduction of additional layers using CMC containing ALE could not reduce the WVP further due to the hydrophilic nature of active coating compound. The moisture absorption behavior of various coated and uncoated PLA samples exposed to 100% relative humidity over 10 days is presented in Figure 5. All samples exhibited an increasing trend in moisture uptake over time. The uncoated PLA sample demonstrated the lowest moisture absorption, reaching only 1.75% after 10 days. This limited uptake is due to the hydrophobic nature of PLA and the absence of sufficient polar functional groups capable of interacting with water molecules. In contrast, the active coated samples absorbed and retained significantly more moisture. This is attributed to the hydrophilic nature of both CMC and ALE. The presence of polar groups in these materials enhances water binding within the matrix. Substituting higher amounts of ALE with CMC led

to even greater moisture absorption, likely due to the combined effects of increased hydrophilicity and structural characteristics.

Figure 5. Moisture absorption behavior of various coated and uncoated PLA samples exposed to 100% relative humidity over 10 days

Antioxidant and antibacterial activity are crucial features of active packaging, helping preserve nutrients and food quality, while also inhibiting microbial growth to extend the shelf life and safety of food products. The coated packaging was tested over time by additional free radicals. After 15 min incubation in the presence of DDPH radicals, only ALE-coated samples showed 40–44% scavenging. Increasing the incubation time to 45 min in presence of additional radicals, showed higher antioxidant scavenging activity (54–67%), attributed to gradual ALE release and its phenolic and flavonoid content. Active packaging also combated microbial contamination. Uncoated PLA and CMC-only coatings had negligible antibacterial effects, while ALE coatings exhibited concentration-dependent inhibition of *E. coli* (0.9–2.1 log reduction) and moderate reduction of *S. aureus* (~1 log). ALE polyphenols likely cause bacterial cell death by disrupting membranes.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrate the successful development of active packaging by coating PLA material with ALE. Surface modification of PLA improved the adhesion of active layers and enhanced the water vapor barrier properties. Coating with CMC/ALE solutions produced uniform, defect-free layers that provided sustained antioxidant activity and concentration-dependent antibacterial effects. These bioactive properties underline the potential of valorizing food loss into sustainable active packaging solutions that preserves food quality and extends shelf life.

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